

Role of Entrepreneurship in Rural Development

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Abstract :

Rural entrepreneurship plays important role in development of rural region of India. India is country in which most of population is depend on agriculture and which is situated in rural area. Agriculture has always been the backbone of the India economy. It provides employment to around 55-60% of the total work force in the country. The rural entrepreneurs with their ability to scan, analyze and identify opportunities in the environment transform them into business proposition through creation of economic entities. They can channelization resources from less productive to move productive use to create wealth. Rural entrepreneurship implies entrepreneurship emerging in rural areas. Establishing new industries in rural areas refers to rural entrepreneurship. In India many examples of successful rural entrepreneurship can already be found in literature.

Introduction :

The word entrepreneur and entrepreneurship have acquired special significance in the context of economic growth in arapidly changing socioeconomic climate in industry in developing countries like India. Entrepreneurial development is a complex phenomenon, productive activity undertaken by him. Entrepreneurs innovate, and innovation is a specific instrument of entrepreneurship. In other words, entrepreneurship is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth by individuals/ group through the use of resources.

Objectives of the study :

1. To analyze the role of Rural entrepreneurship in rural development.
2. To know the problems focusing rural entrepreneurship.
3. To study the measures to promoting rural entrepreneurship.

Research Methodology and data collection :

The study is based on the secondary data for the collection of secondary data the sources newspapers. Tapped were books, journals, magazines and reports related to the purpose of the study. The research paper is conceptual in nature.

Role of Entrepreneurship in Rural entrepreneurship :

1. Provide employment to rural youth :

Rural entrepreneurship is labour intensive and provides a clear solution to the growing problem of unemployment in rural area. Development of agro based industrial units in rural areas through rural entrepreneurship has high potential for employment generation.

2. Balanced Regional Development :

The entrepreneurship always look for opportunities in the rural areas. They capitalize on the opportunities of governmental concession, subsidies and facilities to set up their enterprises in rural and undeveloped region.

3. Imporvement in standard of living :

Enterpreneurial initiative through employment generation leads to increase in income and purchasing power which is spent on consumption expenditure. Increased demand for goods and services boost up industrial activity.

4. Eradication of Poverty :

Entrepreneurs start new industry in rural area can help to eradication of poverty. Poverty reduction and poverty alienation is possible through new employment opportunities in rural areas. To permanently lift people out of poverty.

5. Stop migration of rural population towards urban area:

Rural Entrepreneurship can fill the big gap and disparities in income rural and urban people. Rural Entrepreneurship will develop infrastructural facilities like power, road, bridges, schools etc. It can check the migration of people from rural area to urban areas.

• Problem of Rural Entrepreneurship:

Rural Entrepreneurs are playing very important role in the development of economy. They face various problems in. Some of the major problems faced by Rural Entrepreneurship are as bellow:

1. Lack of infrastructural facilities :

The growth of Rural Entrepreneurship is not very healthy inspite of effort made by government due to lack of proper and adequate infrastructural facilities.

2. Marketing problems. :

Rural Entrepreneurs face severe competition from large size organizations and urban entrepreneurs. They incur high cost of production due to high input cost. They face the problem in fixing standards and sticking to them. New ventures have limited financial resources and hence cannot offered to spend more on sales promotion, advertising.

3. Financial problems. :

Most of the rural entrepreneurs fail to get institutional loan due to absence of security and credit in the market. The procedure to avail loan facility is time consuming. Major difficulties faced by rural entrepreneurs include low level of purchasing power.

4. Legal formalities :

Rural Entrepreneurs find it extremely difficult in complying with various legal formalities in obtaining licenses due to illiteracy.

5. Lack of research and development Facilities:

Rural small scale entrepreneurs cannot get the benefit of research and development facilities like large scale industries.

6. Low productivity :

Small scale entrepreneurs are facing the problems of low productivity They are unable to achieve more productivity with less manufacturing cost at present our productivity is very low.

7. Middleman :

The rural entrepreneurs are depend on middlemen for marketing of their product. Storage facilities and poor means of transport are other marketing problems in rural areas. In most of the villages, farmers store the produce in open space, in bags or earthen vessels. So these methods of storage are not capable of protecting the produce from damage.

8. Unskilled and illiterate labour. :

Rural entrepreneurs of rural areas are unable to find worker with skill. They have to be provided with on the job training and their training is a serious problem for entrepreneurs they are uneducated.

9. Lack of technical knowledge :

Rural Entrepreneurs suffer a severe problem of lack of technical knowledge. Lack of training facilities and extension services create a hurdle for the development of rural entrepreneurship.

Suggestion :

In the view of the above problem rural entrepreneurs the following steps should be taken to improve rural entrepreneurship.

1. The financial institution should provide more financial facilities to rural entrepreneurs.
2. For technological up gradation. Rural entrepreneurs should allow the foreign technological collaboration in small industries. They should take benefit of latest technology. Power of rural consumers so sales volume is insufficient, lack of finance to start business, reduce profit due to competition, pricing of goods and services, lack of guarantees for raising up loans, difficulty in raising capital through loans.
3. Government should provide the infrastructure facilities in rural areas.

4. Rural entrepreneurs should improve their research and development in their product and should take benefit of it with the help of local self government and Non government organization.
5. Proper supply of raw material Rural entrepreneurs should be ensured of proper supply of scarce raw materials on priority basis. A subsidy may also be offered to make the product manufactured by rural entrepreneurs cost competitive and reasonable.
6. Offering training facilities Proper training is essential for the development of entrepreneurship. It enables the rural entrepreneurs to undertake the venture successfully as it imparts required skills to run the enterprise. Local self government NGOs and other voluntary organization can also arrange training programmes for rural entrepreneurs to provide them stimulation counseling and assistance.
7. Create special financial cells in nationalized Bank The financial institutions and nationalized bank, co-operative bank which provide finances to entrepreneurs must create special cells for providing finance to rural entrepreneurs.

Conclusion :

Rural entrepreneurs play an important role in economic development of rural area Rural entrepreneurship is the way of converting developing country into developed nation. Rural entrepreneurship is answer to create employment and eradicate rural poverty in India.

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